

1 **Role of atmospheric resolution in the long-term seasonal variability of the** 2 **Tyrrhenian Sea circulation from a set of ocean hindcast simulations (1997 -** 3 **2008)**

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13 **Keywords**

14 *Mediterranean Sea, Tyrrhenian Sea, regional ocean model, seasonal circulation patterns, atmospheric*
15 *resolution*

16

17 **Abstract**

18 The Tyrrhenian circulation, driven by the interplay of transport at its main straits and local climate,
19 presents a marked seasonal variability. In this work we investigate the role of the horizontal resolution of the
20 atmospheric fields in the long-term seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian Sea circulation. We adopt the eddy-
21 permitting ocean circulation model NEMO-MED12. Simulations cover the 1997 – 2008 period and are
22 driven by atmospheric fields from PROMES regional climate model with a horizontal resolution of 50 km
23 and 25 km. Given that this is the first time that PROMES variables have been used to run ocean simulations,
24 we first evaluate the overall performance of this setup taking into consideration the entire model domain,
25 which covers the whole Mediterranean Sea. We show that PROMES variables allow a good representation of
26 the Mediterranean boundary fluxes and water masses. Focusing on the Tyrrhenian Sea, the comparison of the
27 model results to altimeter data shows that the main features of the seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian
28 large-scale circulation are well captured regardless of the resolution of the atmospheric fields. However, the
29 prescription of 25 km resolution atmospheric fields improves substantially the representation of the
30 dynamical structures resolved by the model. Based on our results, we update intermediate-depth circulation
31 patterns, very little studied so far. We show that changes observed with 25 km fields are not due to a better
32 simulation of transport across Corsica, Sardinia and Sicily straits, but rather to the improved representation
33 of winds.

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 The Mediterranean Sea is a semi-enclosed basin which is connected to the Black Sea through the
37 Marmara-Bosphorus system and to the Atlantic Ocean via the narrow and shallow Strait of Gibraltar (~14 km

38 width, ~300 m depth). The Mediterranean landlocked configuration is exacerbated by the Strait of Sicily,
 39 which communicates the so-called Eastern and Western Mediterranean (Figure 1). On annual basis, the
 40 Mediterranean is subjected to negative surface heat and freshwater budgets (see Jordà et al., 2017 for a recent
 41 review). Surface buoyancy loss entailed by enhanced winter cooling drives open-sea convection, which fuels
 42 the Mediterranean thermohaline circulation (Bergamasco and Malanotte-Rizzoli, 2010). Convection occurs
 43 at specific sites of the Eastern and Western Mediterranean basins and triggers the formation of distinct water
 44 masses with typical hydrographic properties (Skirris, 2014). Schematically, Atlantic Water (AW) enters the
 45 Mediterranean basin at shallow levels above the Strait of Gibraltar and flows into the Eastern Mediterranean
 46 via the Sicily Strait. In the Levantine sub-basin, intense heat loss and evaporation during winter causes
 47 surface waters to sink to intermediate depths (~150 – 350 m) to form the so-called Levantine Intermediate
 48 Water, LIW (Wüst, 1961; Lascaratos et al., 1993; LIWEX group, 2003). LIW flows westward below the
 49 upper AW, increases the salt content at shallow depths and preconditions surface waters for deep water
 50 formation (MEDOC Group, 1970; Wu and Haines, 1996).

51
 52 Figure 1. Bathymetry of the Mediterranean Sea adopted in NEMO-MED12. Names of the different sub-
 53 basins and straits mentioned in the text are superimposed. “EMed” and “WMed” refer to the Eastern and
 54 Western Mediterranean, respectively. Transects across the Corsica (“Cor”), Sicily (“Sic”), Sardinia (“Sar”),
 55 **Bonifacio (“Bon”)** and Gibraltar (“Gib”) straits are highlighted with red bold lines and the corresponding text
 56 is presented in the same colour.

57
 58 In the Western Mediterranean, the Tyrrhenian stands out for its complex geometry and bathymetry
 59 (Figure 1). The Tyrrhenian water column features AW at the surface, LIW at intermediate depths and
 60 Tyrrhenian Deep Water (TDW) at depth (Astraldi et al., 2002; Vetrano et al., 2004). AW and LIW enter and
 61 exit the sub-basin through three openings which are crucial for the water mass exchange between the
 62 different Mediterranean sub-basins: the Strait of Sicily, the Corsica Channel and the Sardinia Channel

63 (Figure 1). Water exchange through these straits, together with local atmospheric forcing over the
64 Tyrrhenian, gives place to a complex circulation pattern which features a marked seasonal variability (e.g.,
65 Krivosheya and Ovchinnikov, 1973; Korres et al., 2000). Over the last decades, observations and numerical
66 models pointed to a winter large-scale surface circulation pattern consisting of a basin-scale, along-slope,
67 cyclonic stream fed by the entrance of AW from the south of the sub-basin (Krivosheya and Ovchinnikov,
68 1973; Artale et al., 1994; Roussenov et al., 1995; Zavatarelli and Mellor, 1995). Whereas most of the AW
69 completes the cyclonic path around the Tyrrhenian and flows out through Sardinia Channel, part of it
70 continues to the north via the Corsica Channel and flows into the Liguro-Provençal sub-basin and then into
71 the Gulf of Lions to form the Northern Current (André et al., 2005). In summer, the described large-scale
72 circulation pattern does not arise and water transport across the Corsica Channel becomes limited (Artale et
73 al., 1994; Vignudelli et al., 1999; Gasparini et al., 2008). The presence of several permanent (or quasi-
74 permanent) and recurrent structures has been reported for decades. For instance, two permanent cyclonic
75 structures to the northeast and southeast of Sardinia are well-known features of this sub-basin (Moen, 1984;
76 Astraldi and Gasparini, 1994). In recent years, the analysis of quality-checked satellite images and results
77 from eddy-permitting ocean general circulation models among others, has revealed that mesoscale processes
78 are of great importance in this sub-basin, especially in summer (Béranger et al., 2004; Rio et al., 2007;
79 Rinaldi et al., 2010; Vetrano et al., 2010; Iacono et al., 2013; Napolitano et al., 2014). New mesoscale
80 structures have been encountered and the seasonal variability of surface circulation patterns has been refined
81 (Iacono et al., 2013; Napolitano et al., 2014; Jouini et al., 2016).

82 Whereas the seasonal evolution of the Tyrrhenian surface circulation is relatively well characterised,
83 intermediate-depth circulation patterns are still poorly constrained. Observations are scarce and geostrophic
84 circulation patterns currently used as reference were already proposed in the early 1970s by Krivosheya and
85 Ovchinnikov (1973) on the basis of hydrographic datasets and in situ measurements. **The work by**
86 **Krivosheya and Ovchinnikov (1973) is one of the most complete reconstructions of the intermediate-depth**
87 **circulation of the Tyrrhenian Sea available to date.** Only a few high-resolution ocean regional circulation
88 models (ORCMs) have been applied to address LIW circulation within the Tyrrhenian (Vetrano et al., 2010;
89 Napolitano et al., 2014). In these works, the simulated time period is not longer than a year and this proves
90 too short to determine whether observed seasonal circulation patterns, which often deviate from the
91 reconstructions of Krivosheya and Ovchinnikov (1973), are representative of the long-term seasonal
92 variability or not. In this context, the application of ORCMs to perform high-resolution hindcast simulations
93 integrated over a sufficiently long time period would constitute an excellent way to achieve a more complete
94 understanding into the most robust features of the seasonal variability of LIW circulation over this sub-basin.

95 In ocean only and coupled ocean-atmosphere simulations applied to the study of the oceanography of
96 the Mediterranean Sea and (or) its sub-basins, atmospheric fields often have a horizontal resolution of 50 km
97 (see www.medcordex.eu). Whereas the use of higher-resolution atmospheric grids is generally advised, this
98 entails important computational costs that are often not affordable, especially in long hindcast simulations or
99 climate projections. **Several modelling works have shown that the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric**
100 **forcing plays an important role in the representation of the ocean circulation in the NW Mediterranean. For**

101 instance, Herrmann and Somot (2008) find that a horizontal resolution of 50 km is required to reproduce
102 deep convection in the NW Mediterranean Sea. This, they argue, relates to the increase of meteorological
103 extremes with higher-resolution atmospheric fields. Béranger et al. (2010) show that the prescription of
104 higher-resolution atmospheric fields allows orographic wind funnelling that intensifies the gyre circulation in
105 the NW Mediterranean and favours preconditioning for deep convection events. The purpose of this work is
106 to study the effect of increasing the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields from 50 km to 25 km on
107 the seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian circulation. Although the system may be subjected to interannual
108 variations, we only tackle the long-term seasonal variability in order to concentrate exclusively on robust
109 circulation features. This allows us (i) to assess the ability of state-of-the-art hindcast simulations to
110 reproduce the long-term seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian surface circulation, (ii) to gain physics-based
111 insight into the very little studied Tyrrhenian intermediate-depth circulation and use the model results to
112 update previously proposed circulation schemes, and (iii) to study circulation changes in response to an
113 increase of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields and analyse the mechanisms that cause them.
114 Specifically, we investigate whether these are driven by an improvement of the strait transport at the
115 openings of the Tyrrhenian Sea and (or) by changes in the regional distribution of the atmospheric fields. To
116 that end, we use the eddy-permitting ocean circulation model NEMO-MED12, which includes the whole
117 Mediterranean Sea. Simulations cover the 1997 – 2008 period and are driven by atmospheric fields obtained
118 from the atmospheric regional climate model (ARCM) PROMES (Domínguez et al., 2013) nested in ERA-
119 Interim reanalysis. PROMES fields, here used for the first time to run ocean simulations, have been
120 evaluated regarding the surface heat and water budgets for the Mediterranean Sea, showing rather good
121 results in comparison with other ARCMs (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2011). This work constitutes an initial
122 effort towards the achievement of a coupled PROMES-NEMO-MED12 configuration.

123 This manuscript is structured as follows. In Section 2, the model setup is described. In Section 3, we
124 briefly evaluate the adequate overall performing of this newly developed setup on the Mediterranean basin-
125 scale. In Section 4, the role of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields in the Tyrrhenian surface
126 and intermediate-depth circulation is tackled. In Section 5, we discuss the effects of the atmospheric data
127 resolution on water properties as well as the causal mechanism responsible for the circulation changes
128 observed with higher-resolution atmospheric fields. A summary of the most relevant findings and some
129 concluding remarks are presented in Section 6.

130

131 2. Model setup

132 In this analysis we use NEMO-MED12, which is a Mediterranean configuration of the Nucleus for
133 European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) v3.2 (Madec et al., 2008). NEMO-MED12 has been formerly
134 adopted to study the large-scale and the mesoscale circulation of the Mediterranean Sea (Beuvier et al.,
135 2012a; Escudier et al., 2016). NEMO is a primitive equation, finite difference, hydrostatic, free-surface,
136 eddy-permitting, three-dimensional ocean model. In NEMO-MED12, the horizontal viscosity coefficient for
137 the dynamics (i.e., velocity) is set to $-1.25 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ m}^4/\text{s}^2$ and is applied with a bi-Laplacian operator. The
138 horizontal eddy diffusivity coefficient for tracers (i.e., temperature and salinity) has a value of $60 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and is

139 prescribed with a Laplacian operator. A 1.5 turbulent closure scheme is adopted for the vertical eddy
140 diffusivity (Blanke and Delecluse, 1993), whereas tracer advection is specified with the Total Variance
141 Dissipation scheme. Bottom friction is parameterised by a quadratic function and a filtered free-surface
142 formulation is used (Roullet and Madec, 2000). Solar radiation can penetrate the sea surface (Bozec et al.,
143 2008). The timestep is set to 12 minutes.

144 The bathymetry adopted has a constant resolution of 30"x30" and derives from the 10th version of the
145 Mercator-LEGOS bathymetry (Figure 1). The horizontal grid is extracted from a global standard three-polar
146 ORCA grid at 1/12° stretched towards a pole located in central Russia. The other two poles are placed in
147 Antarctica and north Canada. The grid presents a non uniform horizontal resolution which varies
148 approximately between 1/14° and 1/18° from 30°N to 46°N, respectively (see Figure 1S of the Supplementary
149 Material). This is roughly equivalent to a resolution ranging from 6.5 km and 8 km in latitude and from 5.5
150 km and 7.5 km in longitude (see Beuvier et al., 2012a for details). Over the Mediterranean Sea, the first
151 Rossby radius of deformation takes values between 10 km and 15 km, being only smaller than 10 km in
152 weakly stratified, coastal regions.

153 Whereas the horizontal grid is finer than the Rossby radius almost everywhere in the Mediterranean
154 Sea, NEMO-MED12 reproduces explicitly processes with a horizontal scale ~5 times greater than its
155 horizontal resolution, meaning structures with a typical horizontal scale of about 40 km or larger. This
156 resolution is sufficient to resolve the most prominent mesoscale structures of the Tyrrhenian sub-basin, most
157 of them with characteristic length scales greater than 100 km (Iacono et al., 2013). In this work, we only
158 address the representation of dynamical structures which are fully resolved by the model. On the vertical, the
159 model has 75 z-levels with partial steps, unevenly spaced. The thickness of the shallowest and deepest model
160 levels are 1 m and 134 m, respectively.

161 To simulate the Mediterranean-Atlantic exchange, a buffer area is implemented over the Atlantic
162 portion of the domain. Within the buffer zone, which extends from -11°E to -6°E, a three-dimensional
163 restoration of potential temperature and salinity towards monthly means of temperature and salinity from the
164 interannual database ORAS-4 (Balmaseda et al., 2013) is performed. To avoid sharp temperature and salinity
165 contrasts between the Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea, the relaxation coefficient varies towards the east
166 from 2 days to 90 days, respectively. To guarantee water volume conservation, sea-surface height within the
167 buffer zone is restored towards monthly means of sea-surface height from ORAS-4. The relaxation
168 coefficient ranges from west to east from 2 seconds to 90 days. River runoff and Black Sea input are
169 specified as a surface discharge at river mouths following the methodology explained in Beuvier et al.
170 (2012a).

171 Atmospheric variables used to run the model derive from two previous simulations performed with
172 the atmosphere regional climate model PROMES (Domínguez et al., 2013) nested in ERA-Interim and
173 carried out as part of MedCORDEX RCM intercomparison project (Ruti et al., 2016). This is the first time
174 that PROMES fields are used to drive ocean simulations. PROMES fields have a horizontal resolution of 50
175 km and 25 km and are available at a frequency of 3 or 6 h—depending on the specific variable. Air-sea
176 interactions are parameterised with bulk formulas, which have been extensively applied to study the

177 oceanography of the Mediterranean Sea (e.g., Nittis et al., 2003; Oddo et al., 2005; Tonani et al., 2008;
178 Napolitano et al., 2016). These bulk formulas use atmospheric data from PROMES and the modelled sea-
179 surface temperature to compute the solar and non solar components of the heat flux, the evaporation rate and
180 the wind stress. We use the Mediterranean Forecast System bulk formulation developed by Castellari et al.
181 (1998), available in NEMO. Required atmospheric variables are: sea level pressure (Pa), total precipitation
182 ($\text{kg/m}^2/\text{s}$), 2-meter air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$), 2-meter dew point temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$), total cloud cover (%) and zonal
183 and meridional components of the 10-meter wind (m/s). Specifically, (i) the solar radiation is computed using
184 Reed (1977) formula, (ii) the net longwave radiation is calculated following Bignami et al. (1995), (iii) drag
185 coefficients used to compute wind stress are calculated according to Hellerman and Rosenstein (1983), and
186 (iv) the latent and sensible heat fluxes are computed with classical bulk formulas parameterised as in Kondo
187 (1975). To avoid a drift in salinity, the freshwater flux (balance between evaporation, precipitation, river
188 discharge and Black Sea input, i.e., E–P–R–B) is corrected. This correction is computed from the relaxation
189 of the model sea-surface salinity towards the sea-surface salinity of the MEDATLAS-II climatology
190 (MEDAR/MEDATLAS Group, 2002). The restoration coefficient is set to $-166.67 \text{ mm/day/psu}$ (Madec et
191 al., 2008). Freshwater flux is not corrected at river mouths. With bulk formulation the modelled sea-surface
192 temperature is used to calculate the surface heat flux and hence a correction of the sea-surface temperature is
193 not required.

194 Starting from an ocean at rest, an 8-year spin-up spanning from the 1st of January 1989 to the 31st of
195 December 1996 is performed. Mediterranean initial conditions for potential temperature and salinity derive
196 from the winter state of the MEDATLAS-II climatology (MEDAR/MEDATLAS Group, 2002). The Atlantic
197 portion of the domain is initialised with monthly means of temperature and salinity from the interannual
198 climatology ORAS-4 (Balmaseda et al., 2013). For the spin-up, atmospheric variables from PROMES with a
199 horizontal resolution of 50 km are used. After the spin-up, two companion simulations are run, differing only
200 in the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields: PR50 (50 km resolution) and PR25 (25 km resolution).
201 Both simulations extend from the 1st of January 1997 to the 31st of December 2008.

202

203 **3. Mediterranean boundary fluxes and water masses**

204 Prior to the examination of the Tyrrhenian sub-basin circulation, as this is the first time that
205 PROMES fields are used to drive an oceanic configuration over the Mediterranean Sea, we ensure the overall
206 performance of this new model setup on the Mediterranean basin-scale. To do so, we concentrate on
207 diagnostics the representation of which is crucial to adequately reproduce the oceanography of the
208 Mediterranean Sea for the simulation time period (e.g., Beuvier et al., 2010). Specifically, we review the air-
209 sea fluxes computed from PROMES fields and the simulated fluxes across the Strait of Gibraltar. We use
210 those fluxes to quantify the Mediterranean heat, salt and water budgets, the closure of which is essential to
211 avoid temperature and salinity drifts. As to the ocean, we address the interannual variations of the basin-scale
212 heat and salt contents, which indicate the ability of this setup to simulate the distinct Mediterranean water
213 masses. For brevity, and because it has been found to be representative of both runs, this validation is done
214 with results obtained from the simulation driven by PR50 fields.

215

216 **3.1. Air-sea fluxes**

217 Here we evaluate the monthly-averaged seasonal cycle of the surface heat flux (W/m^2) and the
218 surface freshwater flux (m/yr) for the simulation period (1997 – 2008). We compare PROMES fluxes,
219 computed as explained in Section 2, to air-sea fluxes calculated from variables obtained from observational
220 datasets. The methodology adopted for the construction of the observational curves presented in Figures 2A
221 and 2B is described in the Supplementary material. A summary of the annual-mean values reported in
222 Section 3, as well as the annual-mean estimates obtained in previous works, is offered in Table 1.

223 The seasonal cycle of the heat flux, given by the addition of the longwave radiation, shortwave
224 radiation, latent and sensible heat fluxes is presented in Figure 2A, in which a positive sign indicates that the
225 ocean gains heat from the atmosphere. The surface heat flux derived from PROMES reproduces well
226 qualitatively and quantitatively the seasonal variability from the observational curves, but is slightly lower
227 than observations in winter and above them in summer. The computed heat flux is positive from March to
228 September with a summer maximum of 171.99 W/m^2 . The heat flux is negative the rest of the year and
229 presents a minimum of -209.02 W/m^2 in December. On average, we find an annual-mean net surface heat
230 flux of -5.48 W/m^2 with an interannual standard deviation of 5.06 W/m^2 . This average and its associated
231 deviation are within the dataset range and are in line with heat flux reconstructions from observational
232 products and from model studies (Table 1).

233

234 Figure 2. Seasonal cycle of the Mediterranean surface heat flux in W/m^2 (A) and surface freshwater flux
235 given in m/yr (B) for the 1997 – 2008 period. Yellow areas are enclosed by two observational curves, blue
236 solid lines correspond to PROMES fluxes and the blue discontinuous line to the mean value of the surface

237 freshwater flux correction computed for the whole simulation time period. Seasonal cycle of Mediterranean
238 outflow (C) and Atlantic inflow (D) at the Strait of Gibraltar (strait transport is computed from -5.50°E and
239 35.60°N to -5.50°E and 36.30°N and is expressed in Sv, 1 Sv= 10⁶ m³/s). Stars in panels C and D indicate the
240 climatological maximum and minimum inflow and outflow volumes reported in Soto-Navarro et al. (2010)
241 for the 2004 – 2009 period.

242

243 The surface freshwater flux, given by the balance between evaporation, precipitation, runoff and
244 Black Sea input, is presented in Figure 2B, in which a positive sign indicates that evaporation exceeds
245 freshwater inputs. PROMES simulates reasonably well the seasonal variability of the net water flux. From
246 March to September, PROMES freshwater flux takes values slightly lower than those computed from
247 observational products. *To understand this small mismatch, it is important to recall that the MEDATLAS-II
248 climatology used to compute the freshwater flux correction extends until 2002. The simulated time period is
249 therefore only partially covered.* The freshwater flux attains a minimum of -0.06 m/yr in May and a
250 maximum of 1.02 m/yr in September. On annual mean, this has a value of 0.59±0.05 m/yr. As observed in
251 Table 1, this is slightly smaller than the means we compute from observational products and is closer to the
252 upper-limit of values derived from observational datasets in Sánchez-Gómez et al. (2011). The blue
253 discontinuous line in Figure 2B displays the mean value of the freshwater flux correction for the whole
254 simulation time period. The computed correction is -0.14 m/yr. The negative sign indicates that, on average,
255 this correction lowers the net evaporation through the addition of water.

256

257 3.2. Transport at Gibraltar

258 The monthly-averaged seasonal cycle of the water transport via the Strait of Gibraltar is presented in
259 Figures 2C and 2D. Values are given in Sv (1 Sv = 10⁶ m³/s) and a positive sign points to transport from the
260 Atlantic into the Mediterranean. Observational data concerning the water transport at Gibraltar are sparse and
261 a continuous record spanning over the simulated time period is not available. To evaluate the computed
262 transports we turn to existing literature. *Water transport at the Strait of Gibraltar, composed by Atlantic
263 inflow into the Mediterranean at the surface and Mediterranean outflow into the Atlantic over the lower
264 portion of the strait, is subjected to a marked seasonal variability.* Mediterranean outflow presents a
265 minimum of -0.64 Sv in February and a maximum of -0.78 Sv in May, giving a seasonal amplitude of 0.14
266 Sv (Figure 2C). A similar timing for the seasonal cycle has been found in observational studies, with
267 maximum and minimum outflow volumes positioned in spring and late fall-winter, respectively (Candela,
268 2001; Soto-Navarro et al., 2010). Atlantic inflow peaks at 0.80 Sv in July and has a minimum value close to
269 0.66 Sv in February, resulting in a seasonal amplitude of 0.14 Sv (Figure 2D). The monthly-averaged cycle
270 for the inflow is also in good agreement with previous works, which report maximum inflow volumes in
271 summer and minimum transport in winter (Bryden et al., 1994; García-Lafuente et al., 2002; Soto-Navarro et
272 al., 2010).

273 For the Atlantic inflow and the Mediterranean outflow we find annual means of 0.75±0.02 Sv and -
274 0.70±0.02 Sv, respectively. These are close to the lower limit of values based on direct measurements at the

275 Strait of Gibraltar, which vary between estimates from Bryden et al. (1994) and Candela (2001), presented in
276 Table 1. As for the water transport, the heat and salt transports at this strait are positive when these are
277 directed towards the Mediterranean. For the net heat transport across Gibraltar we find an annual mean of
278 $5.88 \pm 0.36 \text{ W/m}^2$. The Atlantic is a heat source for the Mediterranean and this is well captured by the model.
279 As observed in Table 1, our estimate is close to the reconstruction of MacDonald et al. (1994) from in situ
280 measurements of water temperature and current velocity across this strait and shows a very good agreement
281 with the ensemble average of Harzallah et al. (2016). For the salt transport at Gibraltar, we calculate 0.002
282 psu/yr , which is an intermediate value between the annual-mean salt transports found in the regional
283 simulations of Beuvier et al. (2010) and Sevault et al. (2014).

284

285 3.3. Water, heat and salt budgets

286 Water volume conservation implied by a closed water budget requires the net surface water flux to
287 equal the net water transport across Gibraltar. In our simulation, both components have an annual-mean
288 value of about 0.05 Sv and the water budget is therefore well closed (Table 1). As in previous model studies,
289 we assume that the heat budget is closed when the imbalance between the net heat gained via Gibraltar and
290 the net heat lost to the atmosphere equals the Mediterranean heat content trend. The latter corresponds to the
291 temperature change from the first to the last year of the simulation divided by the total amount of years
292 considered in the simulated period. As stated above, the net heat transport at Gibraltar and the net surface
293 heat flux are $5.88 \pm 0.36 \text{ W/m}^2$ and $-5.48 \pm 5.06 \text{ W/m}^2$, respectively. For the Mediterranean heat content trend
294 we compute 0.005°C/yr , which equals 1 W/m^2 . The addition of the three components (heat transport through
295 the Mediterranean surface, heat transport through Gibraltar and heat content trend) is 0.6 W/m^2 and the
296 budget is nearly closed. The Mediterranean does not gain or lose salt through the air-sea interface and the salt
297 budget is thus closed when the salt transport at Gibraltar equals the Mediterranean salt content trend. Both
298 terms are 0.002 psu/yr and the salt budget is balanced.

299

300 3.4. Heat and salt contents

301 Figure 3 shows annual series of potential temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$) and salinity (psu) computed from our
302 model results. In this figure, annual means from the EN4 climatology (Good et al., 2013) and the interannual
303 gridded dataset of Rixen et al. (2005) are also presented. Following Rixen et al. (2005), we calculate annual
304 means for the entire Mediterranean basin (Figures 3A and 3B), as well as for several depth ranges (Figures
305 3C – 3H). The first layer extends from the sea surface to 150 m and serves to characterise hydrographic
306 properties of the AW (Figures 3C and 3D). The second one ranges from 150 to 600 m and allows us to
307 evaluate intermediate waters, namely LIW (Figures 3E and 3F). The third one is found from 600 m to the
308 seafloor and is filled with deep waters (Figures 3G and 3H).

309
 310 Figure 3. Annual time series of average temperature given in °C (left column) and salinity expressed in psu
 311 (right column) computed for the entire Mediterranean Sea (A and B), from 0 to 150 m (C and D), from 150
 312 to 600 (E and F) and from 600 to the seafloor (G and H). **The selected depth ranges are representative of the**
 313 **AW, LIW and deep water, respectively.** Blue lines correspond to the model results, black continuous lines are
 314 computed from the EN4 climatology and black discontinuous lines derive from the interannual dataset of
 315 Rixen et al. (2005) with the corresponding uncertainty shaded in yellow.

316
 317 Overall, the model captures well the interannual variability of the Mediterranean basin-average
 318 temperature (Figure 3A). For the simulation time period, computed temperature is qualitatively and
 319 quantitatively close to climatological values with a small warm bias ($\sim 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ in comparison to EN4) which is
 320 not larger than that presented in previous model studies. In the upper layer, temperature exhibits a good
 321 agreement with both climatologies. Temperature estimates are close to those from EN4 and lay within the
 322 uncertainty associated to Rixen et al. (2005) climatology (Figure 3C). Intermediate waters still present a
 323 distinct interannual variability and annual means of simulated temperature resemble observational estimates
 324 (Figure 3E). Temperature of intermediate-depth waters is about 0.1°C warmer than that of the EN4
 325 climatology all over the simulation period. The warm bias encountered for intermediate-depth waters
 326 exhibits a similar magnitude as that found on the Mediterranean basin scale (Figure 3A). This is an indication
 327 that intermediate-depth waters are playing a role in the overall warming of the Mediterranean basin. In the

328 deep basin, interannual variations are weak and temperature mainly shows a small, but progressive, increase
329 with time (Figure 3G). This notwithstanding, simulated temperature estimates are relatively close to
330 observed values and the increase we find is not larger than that reported in previous model studies.

331 Mediterranean average salinity is relatively well represented for the simulated period and presents a
332 small salty bias that does not exceed ~ 0.02 psu relative to EN4 (Figure 3B). In line with previous model
333 studies (e.g., L'Hévéder et al., 2013), simulated interannual variations of salinity have a smaller amplitude
334 than in the climatologies. In the upper and intermediate layers, annual means of salinity are mostly in the
335 range of uncertainty associated to the climatology of Rixen et al. (2005) (Figures 3D and 3F). As for
336 temperature, interannual variations of simulated salinity become less pronounced with depth and, from 600
337 m to the seafloor, these are almost absent (Figure 3H).

338 We can conclude that the model setup we present is able to adequately represent the Mediterranean
339 air-sea fluxes, the water transport across the Strait of Gibraltar and the interannual variability of the different
340 Mediterranean water masses. The biases we report are not larger than those presented in previous studies (see
341 e.g., Beuvier et al., 2010; 2012b; L'Hévéder et al., 2013; Sevault et al., 2014; Harzallah et al., 2016). Water,
342 heat and salt budgets are nearly closed and thus the stability of the run is ensured.

343

344 **4. Ocean behaviour in the Tyrrhenian sub-basin**

345 In this section we study the seasonal surface and intermediate-depth circulation patterns derived from
346 the simulations driven by PR50 and by PR25. To evaluate whether the prescription of PR50 or PR25
347 improves the representation of the surface circulation, the obtained surface patterns are put against
348 geostrophic velocity fields derived from altimeter data. The obtained intermediate-depth circulation patterns
349 are compared to available literature.

350

351 **4.1. Surface circulation over the Tyrrhenian Sea (AW)**

352 Figures 4 and 5 illustrate seasonal averages of salinity and flow trajectories computed from the
353 simulations driven by PR50 and PR25 at a depth of 55 m for the 1997 – 2008 period. This depth is chosen
354 because this is below the frictional Ekman layer and allows us to concentrate on geostrophic features. In
355 these figures, seasonal averages of geostrophic flow trajectories deduced from Copernicus Marine
356 Environment Monitoring System (CMEMS) altimeter data for the simulated time period are also presented.
357 CMEMS provides multimission altimeter gridded sea-surface heights and derived variables over the
358 Mediterranean Sea with a horizontal resolution of $1/8^\circ \times 1/8^\circ$ (www.marine.copernicus.eu). CMEMS data
359 indicates the presence of four dynamical coherent structures (numbered consistently from “1” to “4”), as well
360 as some seasonal structures (numbered “5” and “6”).

362 Figure 4. Winter and spring averages of flow trajectories computed from geostrophic velocities from
363 CMEMS for the 1997 – 2008 period (A and D). Means of salinity (psu) and flow trajectories at a depth of 55
364 m from the simulations driven by PR50 (B and E) and PR25 (C and F), respectively. Red and blue lines and
365 numbers are used to highlight cyclonic and anticyclonic structures, respectively.

366

367 In winter, in agreement with altimeter data and previous modelling and observational works, the
368 large-scale circulation pattern that emerges from the simulations conducted with PR50 and PR25 fields
369 points to a strong, basin-wide, cyclonic stream around the sub-basin (Figures 4A – 4C; see e.g., Krivosheya
370 and Ovchinnikov, 1973; Artale et al., 1994). **Fresh AW enters the Tyrrhenian through the Sardinia Channel,**
371 flows along-slope to the easternmost sub-basin and continues to the northwest until about 10°E and 42°N.
372 From there, part of the flow moves to the north via the Corsica Channel, while part of it flows to the south
373 parallel to the coasts of Corsica and Sardinia until about 10°E and 39°N. From the latter area, water exits the
374 sub-basin through the Sardinia Channel or repeats the described path. Cyclonic structures “1” and “2”
375 develop to the southeast and to the northeast of Sardinia, respectively. These have been identified as
376 permanent or quasi-permanent features (Philippe and Harang, 1982; Artale et al., 1994; Rio et al., 2007;
377 Rinaldi et al., 2010; Vetrano et al., 2010; Iacono et al., 2013; Napolitano et al., 2014). The northern one is the
378 so-called Bonifacio gyre and the southern one, with a more complex geometry, can be regarded as a wide
379 recirculation area connected to other smaller-scale structures, as remarked by Rinaldi et al. (2010). Although
380 both structures are reproduced with PR50 and PR25 fields, they achieve a greater size and are bounded by
381 faster currents with PR25, hence in better agreement with data. The prescription of higher resolution
382 atmospheric fields therefore improves the representation of these structures. In CMEMS data, a relatively
383 small anticyclonic centre labelled as “3” is found to the southeast of “2”. While it is missing in the
384 simulation carried out with PR50 fields, it arises in the simulation driven by PR25 fields. Flow trajectories
385 from altimeter data also show a prominent anticyclonic centre positioned between 12°E – 13°E, to which we
386 refer as “4”. This has been reported in former observational studies as a permanent circulation feature
387 (Budillon et al., 2009; Rinaldi et al., 2010). With PR50 fields, this structure is absent and a flow meander is
388 found instead. However, when atmospheric fields with 25 km resolution are prescribed, structure “4” is
389 correctly reproduced.

390 In spring, the general circulation pattern is similar to that in winter with some minor changes
391 (Figures 4D – 4F). A general decrease of **mean seasonal current velocities** encompassed with an increasing
392 number of the resolved dynamical structures is observed. This notwithstanding, the along-slope, cyclonic
393 stream bordering the sub-basin found in winter is still clearly displayed. Cyclonic structures “1” and “2”
394 arise with both atmospheric collections, but are better simulated with PR25 for the reasons listed above. As
395 in winter, anticyclonic structures “3” and “4” are only captured with PR25. In contrast with winter, flow
396 along the northern coast of Sicily exhibits more meanders and eddies arise over the continental shelf from
397 about 13°E, over the region labelled as “5”. Northwestward flow parallel to the Italian coast appears shifted
398 to the west and small eddies develop, especially to the east of it. The seaward displacement of this stream has
399 also been found in the high-resolution numerical simulations of Napolitano et al. (2014) for spring 2009.

400 In summer, the basin-scale circulation pattern exhibits remarkable differences relative to winter and
401 spring (Figures 5A – 5C). The previously described basin-wide, cyclonic circulation scheme breaks down
402 and a great amount of dynamical structures are simulated. This has also been reported in former model and
403 observational studies in which the basin-scale cyclonic stream has been found to be a winter feature (e.g.,
404 Artale et al., 1994; Iacono et al., 2013). Cyclonic structures “1” and “2” are reproduced with both PR50 and
405 PR25, but the intensification and increase of the zonal extent of structure “2” that emerges from altimeter
406 data in summer, is particularly well represented in the simulation driven by PR25. In summer, “2” and “3”
407 intensify and get attached allowing the clear visualisation of the so-called Bonifacio dipole (Krivosheya and

409 Figure 5. As in Figure 4, but averages are computed for summer and fall.

410

411 Ovchinnikov, 1973; Astraldi and Gasparini, 1994; Rinaldi et al., 2010). With PR50 atmospheric data,
412 velocities are small at the expected location of eddy “3” and no well-defined anticyclonic centre can be
413 identified. On the contrary, with PR25, structure “3”, which was found in all previous seasons with these
414 fields, intensifies substantially and the Bonifacio dipole is clearly depicted. As to anticyclone “4”, current
415 velocities are small and none of the two atmospheric collections tested are able to reproduce enclosed eddies.
416 Besides the commented structures, eddies “5” and “6” stand out as robust summer features. Anticyclonic
417 eddy “5” forms over the northern coast of Sicily. This, which has also been reported in Iacono et al. (2013)
418 and Napolitano et al. (2014), hampers the development of northward flow parallel to the Italian coast. With
419 PR25, anticyclonic centre “5” becomes less intense, more elongated on the zonal direction and achieves a
420 geometry that resembles more that of the corresponding structure from CMEMS data. To the north of “5”, a
421 smaller and less intense anticyclone labelled as “6” is found. With PR25 atmospheric fields, currents that
422 border this eddy intensify improving its representation compared to the case in which PR50 fields are used.
423 In line with previous works, our results support that the appearance of anticyclonic dynamical structures to
424 the east of the sub-basin reverses the flow direction along the Italian coast, which becomes prevalingly
425 southwards (Iacono et al., 2013; Napolitano et al., 2014). Northward transport through the Corsica channel
426 seems too weak or interrupted.

427 In fall, flow velocities over the southern and eastern flanks of the Tyrrhenian increase their
428 magnitude and northward flow along the Italian coast and through Corsica Channel are restored (Figures 5D
429 – 5F). A cyclonic stream around the sub-basin is not fully developed yet. The resolved mesoscale activity
430 decreases relative to summer, but it is still more important than in winter. Cyclonic structures “1” and “2” are
431 intense and, as in summer, “2” shows a remarkable increase of its zonal extension in comparison to winter
432 and spring. In agreement with altimeter data, with PR25 fields, anticyclone “3” is depicted and the Bonifacio
433 dipole is still visible. The dipole does not arise with PR50. Exceptionally, anticyclonic centre “4” is found
434 with PR50, but a pronounced flow meander arises with PR25 instead.

435 From the analysis above we can conclude that the main features of the seasonal variability of the
436 surface large-scale circulation are well captured regardless of the resolution of the atmospheric conditions
437 imposed. The prescription of PR25, however, leads to an improved representation of the most robust and
438 prominent dynamical structures resolved by the model.

439

440 **4.2. Intermediate circulation over the Tyrrhenian Sea (LIW)**

441 Figures 6 and 7 display seasonal averages of salinity and flow trajectories computed from the
442 simulations driven by PR50 and PR25 at a depth of 400 m for the 1997 – 2008 period. This is the depth of
443 maximum salinity, representative of the LIW core. In both figures, the approximate position at which the
444 main surface flow structures were found at shallow levels is indicated with an arrow. The structures are
445 numbered as in Figures 4 and 5. At this depth, currents are slower than at shallower levels (note the different
446 arrow scaling in Figures 4 – 7). LIW enters the Tyrrhenian via the Strait of Sicily, travels to the east and, at

447 about 12.5°E and 38.5°N, coinciding with a bathymetric anomaly, flow bifurcates into two distinct branches
448 regardless of the season: one to the east and one to the west. The branch that flows to the west reaches the
449 westernmost sub-basin through a variable route set by different smaller-scale structures and exits the sub-
450 basin from the Sardinia Channel. At this channel, side-by-side circulation found at shallow depths is replaced
451 by one-directional flow.

452 In winter, LIW enters the Tyrrhenian and flows cyclonically along slope around the sub-basin
453 (Figures 6A and 6B). In contrast to what was found at shallower levels, from 12°E and 41°N, part of the
454 northwestward flow parallel to the Italian coast deflects towards the southwest following topographic
455 contours until 10.5°E and 40°N. In Menna and Poulain (2010), Mediterranean intermediate circulation for the
456 2003 – 2010 period is reconstructed using Argo profiling floats. In spite of the low resolution of Argo data
457 (1°x1°), the described southwestward water branch obtained in our simulations stands out as a robust flow
458 feature. From the latter location, flow continues to the south parallel to the coastlines of Corsica and Sardinia
459 and exits the sub-basin at Sardinia Channel. As in former works, some of the structures found at shallower
460 levels are detectable at intermediate depths (Vetrano et al., 2010; Napolitano et al., 2014). With PR50 fields,
461 the outer contour that defines cyclonic area “1” is still visible at this depth. When PR25 fields are prescribed,
462 the outer contour of “1”, as well as the geometry of structures “2” and “4” are clearly depicted.

463

464 Figure 6. Winter and spring averages of salinity (psu) and flow trajectories at a depth of 400 m for the 1997 –
 465 2008 period obtained with PR50 (A and C) and PR25 (B and D) fields. Red and blue numbers indicate
 466 cyclonic and anticyclonic structures that were also found at shallow depths, respectively.

467

468 Transition from winter to spring entails similar changes to those found at shallower depths (Figures
 469 6C and 6D). Essentially, the winter circulation pattern remains, but current velocities decrease. Northward
 470 flow along the coast of Italy is slightly shifted to the west and small eddies develop to the east of this stream.
 471 The large-scale pattern we report is in agreement with results from the high-resolution numerical simulation
 472 of Vetrano et al. (2010), in which a cyclonic stream around the sub-basin accompanied by a flow branch
 473 crossing from about 12°E and 41°N to 10.5°E and 40°N is found for spring 2004. The flow configuration we
 474 report contradicts Napolitano et al. (2014), in which the flow vein that crosses the sub-basin from east to
 475 west is absent and southward flow parallel to the Italian coast is found for April 2009. This could indicate

476 that April 2009 is not representative of the mean state of the intermediate spring circulation and highlights
477 the necessity of longer simulations to assess robust seasonal circulation patterns. With PR50 and PR25,
478 structures “1” and “2” can still be traced at this depth. Structures “3” and “4”, which appeared with PR25 at
479 shallow depths bounded by currents weaker than in winter, are not visible at 400 m.

480 In summer, as for shallow levels, the overall winter and spring circulation scheme does not develop
481 and a greater number of dynamical structures resolved is detected (Figures 7A and 7B). Cyclonic flow
482 around the sub-basin does not extend further north than about 41°N, where waters deflect to the west. The
483 northernmost sub-basin appears disconnected from the rest. In contrast to what occurs at the surface, flow
484 parallel to Italy does not reverse direction and is still prevailingly northward in summer. With PR50 fields,
485 the outer contour of structure “1” and the signature of eddy “5” on salinity are visible. With PR25, structures
486 “1”, “2”, “3” and “5” are found.

487 In fall, a transition towards the winter circulation starts (Figures 7C and 7D). Currents intensify and
488 dynamical structures become less abundant. Eastward flow parallel to the Sicilian coast extends further to the
489 east. Whereas most of the flow that moves along the Italian coast deflects from 41°N to the west, part of it
490 also continues to the north and completes the longer cyclonic route typical from winter and spring. Whilst
491 with PR50 fields only the external contour of structure “1” is visible, in the simulation driven by PR25,
492 structures “1”, “2” and “3” are represented.

493 As for shallow depths, the main features of the seasonal variability of the large-scale intermediate-
494 depth circulation is well captured with 50 km or 25 km resolution fields, but a greater amount of smaller
495 structures is simulated with 25 km atmospheric fields. Overall, the simulated basin-scale patterns and their
496 seasonal variability show a good agreement with the schemes proposed by Krivosheya and Ovchinnikov
497 (1973) on the basis of composite hydrographic datasets. The fact that the most intense structures found at the
498 surface appear at intermediate depths reflects the barotropic nature of the flow (e.g., Vetrano et al., 2010).
499 Our results highlight that, for a given season, a greater amount of the surface dynamical structures appear at
500 400 m with PR25 fields (Figures 4 – 7). A relevant insight that arises from Section 4.1 is that the prescription
501 of PR25, with some exceptions i.e., summer anticyclonic eddy “5”, generally intensifies surface dynamical
502 structures. This intensification, which is supported by the regional distribution of the sea-surface height (see
503 Figure 2S of the Supplementary material and the accompanying text), causes a greater amount of the surface
504 structures to be visible at this depth. The resolved LIW mesoscale variability that cannot be explained by
505 barotropic impact, may be related to baroclinic instabilities associated with the energetic, cyclonic current
506 that borders the sub-basin or part of it (see Escudier et al., 2016).

507

508 Figure 7. As in Figure 6, but means are calculated for summer and fall.

509

510 5. Discussion

511 In Section 5.1, we investigate the effect of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric data on water
 512 properties. In Section 5.2, we examine whether the improved representation of the dynamical structures
 513 observed with PR25 is driven by changes of the transport at the major Tyrrhenian straits or rather by the
 514 regional distribution of atmospheric fields.

515

516 5.1. Effect of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields on water properties

517 At a depth of 55 m, AW reaches the westernmost end of Sicily with a salinity not higher than 37.7
 518 psu regardless of the season (Figures 4 and 5). Salinity increases within the Tyrrhenian due to “en route”
 519 evaporation. Results from the model study of Napolitano et al. (2014) indicate that AW salinity is maximum

520 to the west of the sub-basin, especially inside cyclone “2”, where vertical mixing with underlying salty
521 waters occurs. In line with that study, we also find an overall salinity increase to the west and maximum
522 values within structure “2”. From this location, salty waters are exported to different areas of the sub-basin,
523 namely to the south. *The improved simulation of dynamical structures with PR25 fields has a concomitant
524 effect on salinity distribution. This can be checked over the northern Tyrrhenian sub-basin where, in winter,
525 salinities close to 38.2 psu are found over a more extensive area with PR25. This is caused by the improved
526 simulation of cyclonic structure “2”, which is stronger and more enclosed with PR25 than with PR50
527 (Figures 4B and 4C).* Changes in the representation of structure “2” also have an impact on the regional
528 distribution of the sea-surface temperature, which is lower and achieves values more consistent with
529 observational data inside it with PR25 fields (see Figure 3S of the Supplementary material and the
530 corresponding text). The latter result stresses the relevance of an adequate resolution of atmospheric models
531 in coupled atmosphere-ocean models in order to achieve a correct heat distribution over the sea surface,
532 which is a primary driver of atmospheric processes.

533 At a depth of 400 m, LIW enters the Tyrrhenian with a salinity close to 38.8 psu (Figures 6 and 7).
534 Salinity is maximum close to the Strait of Sicily, where LIW flows into the sub-basin. At this location, LIW
535 is up to 0.025 psu saltier when PR25 fields are prescribed compared to PR50 fields. This must be related to
536 processes that occur out of the Tyrrhenian sub-basin, namely over the Eastern Mediterranean, where LIW is
537 produced and transported up to the Sicily Strait. From the entrance area, LIW salinity decreases gradually
538 towards the Sardinia Channel due to “en-route” mixing with surrounding fresher waters. Contrary to what
539 happens at shallow levels, salinity decreases from east to west.

540

541 Figure 8. Monthly-mean seasonal cycle of water transport at Sardinia (A), Corsica (B) and Sicily (C) straits
 542 for the 1997 – 2008 period (AW appears in blue, LIW in red and TDW in green). Results from the
 543 simulations driven by PR50 and PR25 are drawn with solid and dashed lines, respectively. The evaluated
 544 transects are: Sardinia (9.04°E and 36.65°N to 9.16°E to 39.60°N), Corsica (9.39°E and 42.90°N to 11.24°E
 545 and 42.81°N) and Sicily (10.88°E and 36.92°N to 12.56°E and 38.00°N).

546

547

548 **5.2. What is needed for an improved representation of the resolved dynamical structures with PR25?**

549 **5.2.1. Seasonal variability of the water transport at the Tyrrhenian Sea straits**

550 Figure 8 shows the monthly-averaged seasonal cycle of water transport at Sardinia (A), Corsica (B)
551 and Sicily (C) straits obtained from the simulations driven by PR50 and PR25 for the 1997 – 2008 period.
552 Positive velocities indicate eastward transport at Sardinia, northward flow at Corsica and southeastward
553 transport at Sicily. For the calculations, the interface between the different water masses is defined as
554 follows. AW–LIW interface is defined by a density of 28.9 (e.g., Vetrano et al., 2004, 2010; Napolitano et al.,
555 2014). At Sardinia Channel, the interface between LIW and TDW is set to 29.1 (Vetrano et al., 2010). We
556 observe that, for a given strait, transports of the different water masses obtained with PR50 and PR25 are
557 almost identical. This finding is in line with results presented in Section 4, which indicate that the seasonal
558 variability of the Tyrrhenian large-scale circulation does not change to a large extent when higher-resolution
559 atmospheric fields are prescribed. In all cases, transports of AW and LIW are maximum in late fall-winter
560 and minimum in summer (Gasparini et al., 2008). A summary of the maximum, minimum and average LIW
561 and AW transports for each of these traits is offered in Table 2. Winter and summer cross-sections of salinity
562 and velocity at the examined straits are presented and described in Figure 4S of the Supplementary material
563 and the corresponding text. In Figure 4S, the resulting position of the interfaces between the different water
564 masses assuming the above described criteria is also depicted.

565 At Sardinia Channel, the seasonal cycle is fundamentally modulated by the transport of AW (Figure
566 8A). Net water transport, which results from the the addition of the transports of AW, LIW and TDW, yields
567 annual means of 0.37 Sv with PR50 and 0.36 Sv with PR25, in line with Vetrano et al (2010). At Corsica
568 Channel, in agreement with observations from Gasparini et al. (2008), water transport is mainly composed
569 by AW and a minor volume of LIW (Figure 8B). We compute an annual-mean net water transport of 0.34 Sv
570 and 0.33 Sv with PR50 and PR25 fields, respectively. Data obtained from mooring and CTD measurements
571 at Corsica Channel from 1985 to 2005 indicate an annual-mean net water transport of 0.49 Sv (Gasparini et
572 al., 2008). The latter value can be considered close to our estimates, especially taking into account that in
573 Gasparini et al. (2008) the greatest transport occurs in the 1980s decade, which is not included within the
574 time period we simulate. At the Strait of Sicily, the calculated annual-mean LIW transports are -0.63 Sv and -
575 0.64 Sv with PR50 and PR25 fields, respectively. These are within the lower range of available values (e.g.,
576 Moretti et al., 1993), but are smaller than -1 Sv, the annual-mean LIW transport found in Gasparini et al.
577 (2008) for the 1993 – 2006 period.

578 Computed transports are adequately reproduced and differences in response to the use of PR50 or
579 PR25 fields are minor. The improved simulation of the resolved dynamical structures with PR25 is thus not
580 linked to a better representation of the strait transport and may be associated with changes in the spatial
581 distribution of the atmospheric fields. This aspect is tackled in the next section.

582

583 **5.2.2. Winds and ocean circulation**

584 Figures 9A – 9F show winter and summer averages of wind direction and wind speed, in m/s,

585 computed for the 1997 – 2008 period making use of PR50 and PR25 fields. In this figure, seasonal averages
586 of wind velocity derived from the Cross-Calibrated Multi-Platform (CCMP) dataset for the simulation time
587 period are also presented. CCMP gridded dataset combines cross-calibrated satellite winds obtained from
588 Remote Sensing Systems (REMSS) and provides winds with a horizontal resolution of $0.25^{\circ} \times 0.25^{\circ}$ (Atlas et
589 al., 2011). In this figure, black discontinuous contours indicate the outer edge of the corresponding surface
590 structures, numbered as in Figures 4 and 5. In all seasons, CCMP winds are highest in the areas adjacent to
591 Sardinia and Sicily straits (Figures 9A and 9D). Wind intensification within this region appears better
592 represented with PR25 (Figures 9C and 9F). Winds from PR50 reach maximum speeds which are always
593 about 0.5 m/s lower than in the CCMP dataset. With PR25, winds attain maximum speeds close to 8 m/s in
594 winter and 6 m/s in summer, both values in agreement with CCMP data.

595

596 Figure 9. Winter and summer means of wind direction and wind speed, expressed in m/s, computed from the
 597 CCMP dataset (A and D), PR50 (B and E) and PR25 (C and F) for the 1997 – 2008 time period. Black

598 dashed lines indicate the geometry of the most prominent dynamical structures found at shallow depths,
599 labelled as in Figures 4 and 5. Red numbers indicate cyclonic circulation and blue numbers the opposite.

600

601 CCMP winds are also particularly intense to the east of the Bonifacio Strait, located close to 9°E,
602 41°N (Figure 1), which is unfortunately not contemplated in this database. In winter, CCMP data indicates
603 the existence of a zonally-oriented wind tongue characterised by maximum speeds of about 7 m/s. The
604 development of this structure may be driven by funnelling of westerlies through the Bonifacio Strait, which
605 is a very well documented phenomena (see Gerigny et al., 2015 and references therein). Focusing on
606 PROMES fields, we observe that wind funnelling through the Bonifacio Strait is only resolved in PR25.
607 Wind intensification due to wind channelling enhances wind speeds to the east of the strait, reaching locally
608 up to 7.5 m/s. In PR50, wind velocities are about 0.5 m/s lower than in PR25. In summer, CCMP winds also
609 exhibit a remarkable intensification over this area, where velocities attain up to 5.5 m/s. Different to winter,
610 in summer, orographic wind funnelling occurs in both PR50 and PR25 datasets. This notwithstanding, wind
611 intensification is more pronounced in PR25. Whereas PR50 winds achieve maximum speeds close to 5 m/s,
612 PR25 winds reach maximum values of about 6 m/s. It is worth to point out that, with PR25, regardless of the
613 season, cyclonic structure “2” positions over the areas where wind speed is high.

614 CCMP winds indicate a slackening to the southeast of the Tyrrhenian sub-basin, where wind speeds
615 are low. Over this area, the regional distribution of winds differs substantially depending on the horizontal
616 resolution of the atmospheric fields. To the north of Sicily, at about 14°E, CCMP winds are not higher than
617 5.5 m/s – 6.5 m/s in winter and 3.5 m/s – 4.5 m/s in summer. In all seasons, PR50 winds are about 0.5 m/s
618 greater than in CCMP, while PR25 winds have almost the same magnitude as in CCMP. Winds from CCMP
619 also show a remarkable velocity gradient around this area and this is better reproduced with PR25. Overall,
620 in line with our results, an improved simulation of winds near the coastlines with higher-resolution
621 atmospheric fields due to a better representation of land-sea gradients has also been found in previous model
622 studies (Obermann et al., 2016; Akhtar et al., 2017).

623

624 Figure 10. Winter and summer **mean** wind work, in cm³/s³, computed for the simulations driven by PR50 (A
 625 and C) and PR25 (B and D) taking into account ocean currents averaged from the surface to a depth of 55 m.
 626 Black discontinuous lines indicate the geometry of the dynamical structures found at shallow depths,
 627 numbered as in Figures 4 and 5. Red numbers indicate cyclonic circulation and blue numbers the contrary.

628

629 To establish a link between the wind representation and the ocean circulation, we now study the
 630 **mean** wind work at play in the Tyrrhenian sub-basin (Wunsch, 1998; Renault et al., 2016). We examine
 631 winter and summer averages of wind work for the simulations driven by PR50 (Figures 10A and 10C) and
 632 PR25 (Figures 10B and 10D). In this figure, the outer contours of the corresponding surface structures are
 633 also superimposed. To compute the **mean** wind work we adopt the following expression:

$$634 \text{ Wind work} = \frac{1}{\rho_o} (\overline{\tau_x u_o} + \overline{\tau_y v_o})$$

634

635 , where ρ_o is the density of sea water, assumed 1020 kg/m³, τ_x and τ_y , the zonal and meridional components of

636 the wind stress, in N/m^2 , and u_o and v_o the zonal and meridional components of the ocean current velocities
637 averaged from the surface to a depth of 55 m, in m/s. In this expression, the overbars indicate long-term
638 seasonal mean values estimated for the 1997 – 2008 period (see Renault et al., 2016). The wind work
639 represents the exchange of kinetic energy between the atmosphere and the ocean and a positive sign indicates
640 that both winds and ocean currents move along the same direction and therefore that wind provides kinetic
641 energy to the ocean. A negative sign, on the contrary, entails that winds reduce the ocean's kinetic energy. In
642 this figure, positive and negative side-by-side values should be interpreted to indicate either the presence of
643 an eddy, water recirculation or wind gradients. As to the large-scale spatial distribution of the wind work, it is
644 greatest (in absolute value) over the near shore region. Regardless of the horizontal resolution of atmospheric
645 fields, in winter, the wind work is positive over the western and southern boundaries of the sub-basin and
646 negative along the eastern Tyrrhenian coast (Figures 10A and 10B). In this season, as concluded in Section
647 4.1, a cyclonic stream that borders the sub-basin develops. This drives northwestward flow along the eastern
648 coast of the Tyrrhenian which moves against winds, namely from the west or the northwest. In summer, the
649 basin-scale cyclonic circulation vanishes and so does the described regional distribution of the wind work.

650 In more detail, in all seasons, wind injects larger amounts of kinetic energy through the western rim
651 of cyclonic structure “2” in the simulation driven by PR25 fields. This is in line with the previously reported
652 intensification of winds in response to orographic funnelling through the Bonifacio Strait with PR25. Also,
653 the regions over which the wind work enhances along the boundary of cyclone “2” appear more extensive in
654 the simulation performed with PR25, especially in summer. The improved representation of structure “2”
655 with PR25 fields, which entails an increase of its size and an intensification of its associated currents (see
656 Figures 4C, 4F, 5C, 5F), can be thus clearly linked to wind activity. This result supports findings from
657 previous studies in which the wind-driven nature of this structure is highlighted (Moen, 1984). In the
658 regional model study of Béranger et al. (2010), the authors report that an increase of the atmospheric forcing
659 resolution allows orographic wind channelling which contributes to the maintenance of a vigorous cyclonic
660 gyre circulation in the Gulf of Lions. Based on the study of the regional distribution of the summer relative
661 vorticity (ζ) for the 1997 – 2008 period, we compute the areas enclosed by the outermost contour that defines
662 structure “2” with PR50 and PR25 assuming a contour interval of $6 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{1/s}$. The surface area of cyclone “2”
663 increases from $2.13 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}^2$ with PR50 to $8.48 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}^2$ with PR25 fields. The computed areas correspond to
664 equivalent radius of 26.07 km and 51.96 km, respectively. Eddy “3”, which is particularly developed in
665 summer and is only clearly reproduced in the simulation driven by PR25, is under the influence of westerlies
666 channelled via the Bonifacio Strait (see Figure 9). In summer, with PR50 fields, the wind work over the area
667 where eddy “3” would be expected is rather small and it does not emerge. With PR25, kinetic energy
668 provided by the wind along its northern boundary enhances and this may favour its appearance. The
669 improved representation of winds through the Bonifacio Strait is therefore responsible for the better
670 simulation of structures “2” and “3”, allowing the development of the summer Bonifacio dipole with PR25.

671 Other structures that are affected by wind representation are anticyclones “5” and “6”. Both arise
672 regardless of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields and constitute robust summer features. As to
673 structure “5”, with PR25, the wind work over its northeastern boundary decreases and the area over which

674 wind injects kinetic energy has a more elongated geometry relative to the simulation driven by PR50. This is
675 consistent with the improved representation of the wind velocity gradients over this region due to wind
676 slackening with PR25. The slowdown of eddy “5” observed with PR25, consistent with CMEMS geostrophic
677 velocities, is thus in agreement with the observed changes in the wind activity. To the north of “5”,
678 anticyclone “6” arises. With PR25, eddy “6” slightly intensifies and this structure, together with eddy “5”,
679 form a summer dipole which is not so well represented with PR50.

680 To further assess the role of local winds in the improvements observed in the Tyrrhenian circulation
681 with higher-resolution atmospheric fields, we now examine summer time series of wind stress curl (A) and
682 eddy kinetic energy, EKE, **computed making use of daily means of ocean velocity, as well as the mean ocean**
683 **currents for the 1998 – 2007 period (B)** over the Tyrrhenian sub-basin (Figure 11). This analysis concentrates
684 on the summer season because the winter circulation pattern is prone to AW stream instabilities rather than
685 local atmospheric forcing, as shown by Iacono et al. (2013). Furthermore, in summer, the improved
686 representation of dynamical structures is more remarkable than in other seasons.

687
688 Overall, in the simulations driven by PR25 fields, wind stress curl and EKE present higher values
689 than with PR50 fields, thus in better agreement with observational data. The correlation coefficient between
690 simulated and CCMP wind stress curl increases from 0.63 with PR50 to 0.70 with PR25 fields. Wind stress
691 curl mean biases for the simulation time period decrease from $-4.91 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ N/m}^3$ with PR50 to $3.64 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ N/m}^3$
692 with PR25. In agreement with former modelling studies performed with NEMO-MED12 (e.g., Beuvier et al.,
693 2012a), simulated EKE levels are lower than those from CMEMS. This notwithstanding, the prescription of
694 higher-resolution atmospheric fields improves substantially its representation. The correlation coefficient
695 between simulated and CMEMS EKE takes values smaller than 0.10 with PR50 and 0.56 with PR25 fields.
696 Also, mean biases **decrease in magnitude** from $-15.08 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ with PR50 to $-7.21 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ with PR25 fields.
697 Figure 11 also shows that high (low) values of wind stress curl often coincide in time with an increase
698 (decrease) of the EKE levels. The correlation coefficient between the wind stress curl from CCMP and the
699 simulated EKE is greater than 0.50 regardless of the atmospheric field resolution. Although there may be
700 different factors controlling changes in the EKE, wind stress curl is clearly at play.

701

702
 703 Figure 11. Summer time series of wind stress curl in N/m^3 (A) and EKE in cm^2/s^2 (B) over the Tyrrhenian
 704 sub-basin. Blue and red curves are constructed from results derived from the simulations driven by PR50 and
 705 PR25 fields, respectively. Green lines are built making use of data from CCMP (A) and CMEMS (B). Wind
 706 stress curl curves are created from the zonal and meridional components of the wind stresses from the
 707 simulations driven by PR50 and PR25, as well as from the CCMP dataset. EKE time series are constructed
 708 from the zonal and meridional components of the ocean velocities from PR50 and PR25 averaged from the
 709 surface to a depth of 55 m, as well as from the geostrophic currents from CMEMS.

710

711 6. Summary and conclusions

712 This work is dedicated to the study of the role of the horizontal resolution of the atmospheric fields
 713 in the long-term seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian Sea circulation. To that end, we adopt the eddy-
 714 permitting ocean circulation model NEMO-MED12, which is a Mediterranean configuration of NEMO, and
 715 high-resolution atmospheric fields from PROMES regional climate model nested in ERA-Interim. We
 716 examine two companion simulations that cover the 1997 – 2008 period and only differ in the horizontal
 717 resolution of the atmospheric fields, which is 50 km (PR50) or 25 km (PR25). Because PROMES fields are
 718 here used for the first time to simulate the oceanography of the Mediterranean Sea, the overall performance

719 of this novel setup is examined prior to the study of the Tyrrhenian Sea circulation. We show that the
720 presented configuration reproduces conveniently the seasonal cycle of the Mediterranean air-sea fluxes and
721 the transports across the Strait of Gibraltar. The interannual variability of the distinct Mediterranean water
722 masses is relatively well simulated and the biases we report are not larger than those found in previous
723 studies. The most relevant findings extracted from the examination of the Tyrrhenian circulation, the primary
724 focus of this study, with this particular configuration are:

725 - The seasonal variability of the Tyrrhenian basin-scale circulation is well captured with PR50 or PR25, but
726 the representation of the resolved dynamical structures is improved with PR25 fields.

727 - In line with CMEMS geostrophic velocities, the winter and spring large-scale surface circulation patterns
728 are characterised by a broad cyclonic stream around the sub-basin which does not arise in summer and fall
729 regardless of the resolution of the atmospheric fields.

730 - The prescription of PR25 improves the geometry, position and velocity of the simulated ocean dynamical
731 structures at shallow levels.

732 - Intermediate-depth circulation patterns from the simulations driven by PR50 and PR25 fields for winter-
733 spring and summer-fall, respectively, show a good agreement with schemes from Krivosheya and
734 Ovchinnikov (1973). In winter and spring, most LIW flows cyclonically around the Tyrrhenian and only a
735 minor part of it crosses the sub-basin from about 12°E and 41°N to 10.5°E and 40°N. In summer and fall,
736 most LIW deflects to the southwest and the northern domain of the sub-basin becomes isolated.

737 - Only the most prominent surface flow structures are found at intermediate depths. The use of PR25 fields
738 generally intensifies them and therefore a greater amount of the surface eddies, gyres and meanders are
739 reproduced with PR25 at a depth of 400 m.

740 - The presence (or absence) of structures such as gyres and eddies, as well as their geometry and velocity,
741 exert a first-order control in the regional distribution of salt and heat. In coupled atmosphere-ocean models it
742 is advisable that atmospheric grids have a resolution greater than 50 km in order to achieve a correct
743 distribution of heat over the sea surface, which is a primary driver of atmospheric processes. For uncoupled
744 ocean simulations not focused on mesoscale-size processes, atmospheric fields with 50 km would seem
745 sufficient.

746 - Improvements in the simulation of the most robust dynamical structures with PR25 are not linked to
747 changes in the transport across Sardinia, Corsica and Sicily straits, but rather relates to the better simulation
748 of winds.

749 - Changes in the regional distribution of the wind work explain, to a large extent, the improved
750 representation of the dynamical structures observed in the simulation driven by PR25.

751 In view of our results we can conclude that, although there is room improvements, the overall
752 performance of the presented model setup is quite satisfactory. Because conclusions drawn could be to some
753 extent model dependent, future work will potentially include a multimodel analysis in the frame of
754 MedCORDEX. This will allow us to get insight into the consistency of results obtained with PROMES
755 atmospheric data and results derived from other model configurations. An interesting follow-up of this work
756 could include a quantification of the eddy wind work, the barotropic conversion from mean kinetic energy to

757 **EKE and the baroclinic conversion from eddy potential energy to EKE.** A current effort is being done to
 758 achieve a PROMES-NEMO-MED12 coupled configuration.

759

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 766 CMEMS, EN4, MEDATLAS II, and Rixen et al. (2005). We are grateful to the reviewers for their insightful
 767 comments.

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769

770 **Table 1.**

	Strait of Gibraltar					Mediterranean Sea			
	Water flux in (Sv)	Water flux out (Sv)	Water flux net (Sv)	Heat flux net (W/m ²)	Salt flux net (psu/yr)	Surface heat flux (W/m ²)	Surface water flux (m/yr)	Heat cont. trend (W/m ²)	Salt cont. trend (psu/yr)
This study (model results)	0.75±0.02	-0.70±0.02	0.047±0.008	5.88±0.36	0.002	-5.48±5.06	0.59±0.05 (0.048 Sv)	1	0.002
This study (observational products)	--	--	--	--	--	-3.69±7.02 to -10.10±10.19	0.76±0.07 to 0.71±0.08	--	--
Bryden et al. (1994)	0.72±0.16	-0.68±0.15	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
Candela (2001)	1.01	-0.97	0.04	--	--	--	--	--	--
Soto-Navarro et al. (2010)	0.81±0.06	-0.78±0.05	0.038±0.007	--	--	--	--	--	--
Harzallah et al. (2016)	0.74	-0.70	0.04	4.88	--	-4.76±1.68 to 2.15±2.37	--	--	--
Boukthir and Barnier (2000)	0.77	-0.74	0.03	--	--	--	--	--	--
Macdonald et al. (1994)	--	--	--	5.2 ±1.3	--	--	--	--	--
Garrett et al. (1993)	--	--	--	7±3	--	--	--	--	--
Sánchez-Gómez et al. (2011)	--	--	--	--	--	-15±6 to 9±8	0.28±0.11 to 0.66±0.11	--	--
Beuvier et al. (2010)	--	--	--	--	0.0009	--	--	--	--
Sevault et al. (2014)	--	--	--	--	0.003	--	--	--	--

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Table 2.

		AW_{\max}	LIW_{\max}	AW_{\min}	LIW_{\min}	AW_{av}	LIW_{av}
Sardinia	PR50	$1.60 \cdot 10^6$	$-5.10 \cdot 10^5$	$3.51 \cdot 10^5$	$-3.05 \cdot 10^5$	$(9.35 \pm 1.17) \cdot 10^5$	$(-3.95 \pm 1.76) \cdot 10^5$
	PR25	$1.55 \cdot 10^6$	$-5.02 \cdot 10^5$	$3.25 \cdot 10^5$	$-2.99 \cdot 10^5$	$(9.11 \pm 1.22) \cdot 10^5$	$(-4.05 \pm 1.44) \cdot 10^5$
Corsica	PR50	$7.07 \cdot 10^5$	$4.06 \cdot 10^4$	$-5.80 \cdot 10^4$	$-1.97 \cdot 10^4$	$(3.40 \pm 0.68) \cdot 10^5$	$(0.34 \pm 1.19) \cdot 10^4$
	PR25	$6.91 \cdot 10^5$	$2.13 \cdot 10^4$	$-3.98 \cdot 10^4$	$-1.40 \cdot 10^4$	$(3.30 \pm 0.67) \cdot 10^5$	$(0.41 \pm 0.73) \cdot 10^4$
Sicily	PR50	$7.33 \cdot 10^5$	$-8.38 \cdot 10^5$	$3.64 \cdot 10^5$	$-4.67 \cdot 10^5$	$(5.14 \pm 1.80) \cdot 10^5$	$(-6.32 \pm 1.85) \cdot 10^5$
	PR25	$7.22 \cdot 10^5$	$-8.35 \cdot 10^5$	$4.14 \cdot 10^5$	$-4.72 \cdot 10^5$	$(5.31 \pm 1.74) \cdot 10^5$	$(-6.38 \pm 1.83) \cdot 10^5$

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Table captions

783 Table 1. Compilation of the heat, salt and water budget components computed in this study, as well as values
784 presented in previous works. Fluxes at Gibraltar are positive when the transport is directed towards the
785 Mediterranean Sea. The surface heat flux is positive when ocean gains heat from the atmosphere. A positive
786 surface freshwater flux indicates that evaporation prevails over precipitation and river discharge.

787

788 Table 2. Maximum, minimum and average transports, in m^3/s , with the associated interannual standard
789 deviation of AW and LIW at Sardinia, Corsica and Sicily straits obtained with PR50 and PR25 fields (1 Sv =
790 $10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$).

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